

Using the Systems Modelling Language (SysML) for Decision Modelling for Sustainable Building Design

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ABSTRACT:

Sustainability requires the inclusion of appropriate engineering models in the early design phases to allow a performance driven design. This paper presents a method to observe the design process to determine the requirements for parametric performance models for early design phases. The method is based on the Systems Modelling Language (SysML). It starts from a recording of the design process by activity diagrams, includes dependencies and information exchange and finally uses parametric diagrams to outline decision-tailored performance models. A design example, the high-rise building “Haikou Tower” design by the office Studio B serves as data source to illustrate the method.

1 INTRODUCTION

Sustainable building design is one of the major challenges of current planning and construction. Our built environment causes a large part of energy and resource flows. Despite major development, such as Building Information Modelling, the AEC industry is still fragmented. This has been observed as an obstacle for the economic performance of this sector. Furthermore, computer-support has been identified as remedy for this situation (Howard et al. 1989, Bédard 2006).

A similar situation turns up in sustainable building design. The problem of fragmentation shifts from the construction phase to the design phase of a building. In this phase the integration of the architectural design with engineering involving relevant disciplines is required. For instance, the rating system by the German council sustainable building (DGNB 2012) shows indicators for assessing building designs in terms of their sustainability that illustrate the multidisciplinary character of the design process and the involvement of the different disciplines to interact in the design process and its inherent decision making.

In this situation, the paper presents an analysis approach to record the decisions, the involved disciplines and tools in design processes including their chronological order as well as their dependencies. The aim is to capture decisions relevant for sustainability, to determine the concerned disciplines and to

identify relevant patterns and required decision-supporting models. This information forms the basis for the development interdisciplinary system-based models in future research. These models are specifically developed for the decision situation and thus are able to support the design process in an appropriate way.

The hypothesis of this approach is that design decisions have a major influence on the sustainability of buildings and the support by sustainability tools needs to follow the requirements of the design process with its activities and decisions. Due to this reason, this paper develops a method to model the design process by means of the Systems Modelling Language (SysML, OMG 2012).

Some studies and methods tackle decision making in its importance to sustainable building design. Magent et al. (2009) develop their own notation and describe some patterns in design processes that concern sustainability. Gane and Haymaker (2010) benchmark the processes of high-rise buildings by quantitative indicators including aspects of sustainability. Haymaker et al. (2006) present an approach recording dependencies as “narratives” following a process-related approach. Hwang et al. (2013) empirically observe design processes of “green buildings” and identify process-related shortcomings. Baldwin et al. (2008) use process modelling to reduce construction waste. Finally, the NIST’s Integration Definition for Function Modeling (IDEF0) presented a widely-used standard similar to the ac-

tivity diagrams from SysML used in this paper; however, IDEF0 is not as flexible as the tools by the SysML. Among these papers there is no empirical observation and modelling of the decision processes in designing with the aim of developing system models tailored for decision-making.

The paper belongs to a research focus of using systems engineering for sustainable building design and construction (Geyer 2012 and Geyer and Buchholz, 2012, Geyer et al. 2014). This paper focuses on the consideration of the decision making process, the involved stakeholders and tools. The aim of the research approach is to complement the systems modelling approach by a method of implementing it in the design process and its decision making. The method presented in this paper is intended to identify the impact of decisions on the sustainability of

buildings and the need for integrative decision-driven system models.

The method of recoding the design process and of identifying patterns and required models for key decisions in terms of sustainability is shown by one exemplarily case of a design process of the high-rise “Haikou Tower” designed by the architectural office Studio B. building. Rather the serving for direct empirical deduction, this unique case exemplifies the approach and provides material to illustrate the method for the identification of patters and required models. The case is a vehicle to transport the idea of deriving required decision-tailored models from process patterns. Experience of actors involved in the process constitutes a source of generality for the patterns.

Figure 1. Partial sequence diagram (sd) of the design process showing the activity of tools, criteria, disciplines and paramters.

2 OBSERVATIONS OF THE DESIGN PROCESS

The basis for the requirement-driven development of decision-supporting system models is the observation of design processes. The observation presented in this section form the basis for the recognition of typical patterns and the identification of decision relevant for sustainability. The process models that are in parts shown in this section represent one instance of a design process of a high-rise building.

2.1 Sequences

The first model shown as excerpt in Figure 1 is a sequence diagram recording the activity of design tools, design criteria, involved design disciplines, and concerned design parameters of the high-rise building during the design process in its chronological order. It equals to some extent an Gantt chart describing activities over; however, it is an observation retrospectively constructing the design process without providing the content of the activities. The main

intent of this model is to examine the phases of designing and the activity of the different entities at the same time. In detail, Figure 1 shows the transition from a design phase determining the geometry of the building body to the design of the building envelope (façade, roof etc.). The structural design is finished (e.g. shown by the end of activities such as a second work phase called “Structure II”) and consideration on energy, climate (“Climate I”) and the design of the façade start (“Façade I”). Whereas before the focus was structural feasibility (Figure 1, “Design Criteria”) now it shifts to the energy consumption, comfort and cost.

2.2 Activities, dependencies and exchange

The activity diagram (act) from SysML plays a central model of the approach. It serves to model the steps of designing with its contents, its logical interdependencies and its exchange of information. This allows to examine the real dependencies between design activities. This first type of activity model still fol-

Figure 2. Activity diagram with process contents and dependencies including information exchange.

Figure 3. Decision chain, i.e. the logical structure of design steps observed for the high-rise building design.

low an observation paradigm, which means that activities and exchanged information from the mentioned instance of the design process where captured in chronological order. Figure 2 shows a part of this second model. It includes activities, such as the Façade Workshop II, with information inputs (façade module 3D file, renderings, updated massing model and MEP concept) as well as outputs (refined details and implementation of climate). This material allows to get an idea what decisions were made in the activities and how the dependencies of the design evolve in time. This phase shows the transition of the design of the envelope to the end of the design. The façade (“Façade II”) and the climate engineering (“Climate Engineering Conference Call”) are finalized with the data of the energetic performance and the details for the envelope of the building to form data for the final submission, which are input to the process “Prepare Final Submission”. There is also an exchange from the climate engineering to the façade transporting requirements for the façade.

3 DECISION STRUCTURES

The previous section mainly takes an observing point of view. In contrast, this section tackles the reconstruction to the logical structure of the design decisions. It is assumed that the design process consists of subordinate decision processes and partial solution definitions that interact. Furthermore, these solutions occur in a hierarchical structure. The Structure is defined first, which is reasonable for a high-rise building. Then processes of floor plan design and façade design including comfort and energy fol-

low. This will probably differ for other types of buildings.

3.1 The logical network of decisions

The first step for this change of the point of view is the shift from the time-based perspective to a dependency-based perspective. The mentioned hierarchy leads as consequence to dependencies between the design activities that require the one design step being carried out before the other or, in interactions, subsequent design steps being repeated if a high-level definition is changed.

To model this, in addition to the element ‘action’, which is standard for the activity diagram in SysML, the stereotype ‘solution’ is defined. Whereas the activity represents the design activities carried out by architects and engineers, the solution represents partial design definitions concerning a partial element or system of the building that were taken as being fixed for the moment. This is a core element of the iterative nature of designing to assume certain elements fixed and then to proceed exploring if suitable overall solutions follow. It does not mean that these solutions are in the course of the design process revised. With these elements, the activity diagram (act) of the SysML provides an adapted to describe the design process logically.

Figure 3 shows the structure derived from the observation material using this extended activity model. This network structure provides an overview of the whole design process with one level of abstraction, which is the logical structure describe above; the history-like view is replaced by a systemic view. Design iterations as well as time-based processes, such as shown in the Figures 1 and 2, were filtered

out. Instead the overall logical dependencies shift into focus. After processing the design requirements (Figure 3, left), three core activities follow, which are the decision on the height and the footprint of the building, the design of the external geometry and the layout of the floor shapes. An important result of these activities is the external geometry of the building body that is shown on the drawing at bottom left in the figure. This forms the basis for three further strands of design activities: The first one deals with the façade, the second with the structural system of the building and the third one with the floor plan of each storey. The façade can be designed independently to a certain degree as soon as the building body is defined. The definition of the structural system comprises two subordinate solutions, which are the vertical and the horizontal load system. The structure has a dependence on the loads from the façade. The design of the floor plans again depends on the position and form of the structural elements. These strands all converge in the final design.

3.2 Models for decisions

The previous subsection defined a network of decision that underlies the design process. To make these decisions in a well-founded way, there is the need for models that deliver information supporting the decisions. These models need to fit the current design state, i.e., they should be able provide an evaluation considering the known details, information and definitions at the state of designing and not require details that are not available. Furthermore, they should deliver the desired information for decision making quickly and in a concise way. Finally, a quick analysis response and thus the generation of variants should be easy.

The method of Parametric System Modelling (PSM, Geyer 2012 and Geyer and Buchholz, 2012) is especially developed for this purpose to complement geometry-focused CAAD by the multidisciplinary engineering for energy efficiency and sustainability embedded in the design process. This approach is applied in a decision oriented way. Figure 4 shows a parametric model tackling the situation of the façade design described in the first stand in Figure 3. It abstractly describes a parametric model determining the façade performance. The model depends on the typical parameters such as orientation, climate, thermal loads as well as shading, ratio of windows to opaque, insulation and materials as well as façade-integrated systems of renewable energy. From these parameters, it determines the energy performance and resulting environmental effects as well as the life cycle costs (LCC) and comfort. This can be achieved by applying simulation or better by metamodels (surrogate models, see Geyer and Schlüter 2014) that respond more quickly. Such a tailored model provides infor-

mation in a more appropriate way that a detailed building performance simulation.

Figure 4. Parametric decision-oriented model determining the façade performance.

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

In sum, the paper represents an approach to model and analyze the design and planning process of buildings with the aim of deriving decision-tailored supporting engineering models. The emphasis is put on identifying impacts and needs in terms of sustainable building design. This allows observing the decision making processes, to identify key patterns and, on this basis, to derive the performance analysis models and to setup integrative system models made for the needs of decision making. Three steps of the method lead from the chronological observation to the decision-supporting model. First, the activities are complemented by dependencies and information exchange. Second, the chronological view is replaced with a logical structure. Third, for key nodes of the structure, information requirement and available information allow the setup of models tailored for the decision situation. This allows a better support of the design process by performance information in early phases. Appropriate engineering models from different disciplines are integrated to provide valuable information and discipline-crossing dependencies. Thus they provide a basis for developing the interdisciplinary modelling approach required for sustainable design.

5 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author thanks the office ‘Studio B’ to allow insight and to support the observation of the design process of the high-rise building project Haikou Tower. Furthermore, the project was funded by the Volkswagenstiftung in the program “Computational

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